

Milan System for Reporting Salivary Gland Cytology with an Emphasis on Histopathological Correlation: A Comparative Study in Rural West Bengal**Rajarshi Bhattacharyya¹, Sabyasachi Majee², Trisha Banik³, Agnik Pal⁴**¹Associate Professor, Department of Pathology, Santiniketan Medical College, Bolpur, West Bengal 731204²Assistant Professor, Department of General Medicine, ESIC Medical College, Joka, Kolkata, West Bengal 700104³Associate Professor, Department of Pathology, ESIC Medical College, Joka, Kolkata, West Bengal 700104⁴Associate Professor and Head, Department of Pharmacology, Santiniketan Medical College, Bolpur, West Bengal 731204

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Abstract:

Fine needle aspiration study is a very useful technique for detecting palpable lesions. In our study, 164 patients hailed from rural areas with salivary gland enlargement referred to the Department of Pathology were included and Fine Needle Aspiration Cytology (FNAC) investigation yielded 82 (50%) non-neoplastic lesions, 78(47.56%) neoplastic lesions and 4 (2.4%) inconclusive lesions on cytology. The most commonly involved site was parotid gland (110, 67.07%), followed by submandibular gland (50, 30.48%) and minor salivary glands (4, 2.4%). 60 (36.5%) patients underwent surgical excision and specimens were available for histopathological correlation. Grading of salivary gland tumors were done according to the Milan System for reporting salivary gland cytology. Accuracy rate for non-neoplastic lesion was 61.53%, for benign neoplasms 85.3%, and for malignant neoplasms 66.6%.

Keywords: Fine Needle Aspiration Biopsy, Cytology, Milan System, Salivary gland, Neoplasm, Histopathology.

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Introduction

Fine needle aspiration cytology is a reliable, safe, inexpensive and widely accepted pre-operative diagnostic tool in the diagnosis of salivary gland lesions. Because of their strategic location, salivary glands are easy targets for aspiration. The morphological diversity of salivary gland neoplasms poses a great challenge in the diagnosis and classification of these lesions on FNAC. Stewart [1] was the first to publish a paper on cytodiagnosis of salivary gland lesions following which there were a series of publications.

When FNAC is used to subclassify the different salivary gland neoplasms, the accuracy ranges widely from 48% to 94% in different studies.[2] The manifestations of basaloid cell component, squamous metaplasia, oncocytoid changes, cystic component etc. are different cytomorphological features that make FNAC a diagnostic challenge. There are many studies proposing use of morphological pattern-based analysis to develop a risk stratification approach for classification of salivary gland neoplasm and providing risk of malignancy and to guide for further ancillary test

and management plan.[3] To address a standard terminology for reporting salivary gland cytopathology and making easier for the clinicians to approach for the management strategies, The American Society of Cytopathology and International Academy of Cytology proposed a tiered international classification scheme called the "Milan System for Reporting Salivary Gland Cytopathology" (MSRSGC), providing guide for clinical management according to risk of malignancy in different categories.[4,5]

The present study, spanning over a period of five years, was undertaken to evaluate the efficacy of FNAC in detecting salivary gland lesions by comparing with histopathological study using this MSRSGC approach. The cytological features were evaluated, and cases were reclassified according to MSRSGC [4] as follows: Category 1: Non-diagnostic, Category 2: Non-neoplastic, Category 3: Atypia of undetermined significance, Category 4a: Neoplasm: Benign, Category 4b: Neoplasm: Salivary gland neoplasm of uncertain malignant potential, Category 5: Suspicious of malignancy and

Category 6: Malignant. Histopathological data wherever available were corroborated as histological diagnosis is considered as gold standard.

Materials and Methods

164 patients with salivary gland enlargement hailed from rural areas of West Bengal and who were referred to the Department of Pathology in a tertiary care medical college hospital were included in the study. After obtaining informed consent of all the patients, FNAC was carried out from the salivary gland enlargements. Smears were stained by Haematoxylin & Eosin stain. 60 surgically resected specimens were available for histopathological correlation. They were routinely processed and

stained with Haematoxylin & Eosin stain. Smears with no histopathological correlation were reviewed. Then Classification and reporting was undertaken according to MSRSGC grading system.[4] It is a six-tier classification providing a standardized terminology and ROM for each category and thus avoiding the ambiguity often seen in FNAC interpretation.

Results

Demographic parameters are shared in Table 1 and Figure 1. In the present study there was a slight female preponderance, most cases belonged to 4th - 5th decades.

Table 1: Age and sex distribution of salivary gland lesions

Years	Male	Female	Total
< 10	02	-	02
11-20	04	02	06
21-30	09	09	18
31-40	10	26	36
41-50	22	26	48
51-60	18	21	39
61-70	06	08	14
71-80	01	-	01
Grand total	72	92	164

Figure 1: Age and sex distribution of salivary gland lesions

Site and nature of the lesions according to the salivary glands involved are shared in Table 2 and Figure 2.

Table 2: Site and nature of lesion

	Parotid Gland	Submandibular Gland	Minor Salivary Gland	Total
Non-Neoplastic	52	26	04	82
Neoplastic	55	23	-	78
Lesion Could Not Be Ascertained On Cytology	03	01	-	04
Total	110	50	04	164

Among the involved glands in decreasing order of frequency are parotid (110 cases, , 67.07%), submandibular (50 cases, 30.48%) and minor salivary glands (4 cases, 2.4%). FNAC revealed higher incidence of non-neoplastic lesions (82 cases, 50%) as compared to neoplastic lesions (78 cases, 47.56%). 4 lesions (2.4%) were inconclusive on cytology.

Figure 2: Site of lesion

Incidences of benign neoplasm are depicted in Figure 3 and incidences of malignant neoplasm are depicted in Figure 4. Among non-neoplastic lesions inflammatory lesions were most common accounting to 51 cases (62.1%), followed by benign cystic lesions with 29 cases (35.3%) and 2 (2.4%) non-specific cases. Among neoplasms benign (71

cases, 91.02%) were more common than malignant (7 cases, 8.9%). Among benign neoplasms pleomorphic adenoma was most common with 61 cases (78.2%), followed in decreasing order of frequency: monomorphic adenoma and myoepithelioma (3 cases each, 3.84%), oncocytoma and benign cystic neoplasm (2 cases each, 2.56%).

Figure 3: Incidences of benign neoplasm

Among malignant neoplasms in decreasing order of frequency are Mucoepidermoid carcinoma (4 cases, 5.1%), Carcinoma ex pleomorphic adenoma (2 cases, 2.5%), Acinic cell carcinoma (1 case, 1.28%). 4 lesions could not be diagnosed on FNAC.

Figure 4: Incidence of malignant neoplasms

Histopathological Correlation

The histopathological correlation of different salivary gland lesions are depicted in Tables 3-6. Of the 82 non-neoplastic lesions, 13 excised specimens were available for histopathological correlation. 3 cases were sialadenitis and 13 cases were benign cystic lesion. All sialadenitis showed 100% correlation. 5 benign cystic lesions turned out to be mucus retention cysts while out of the other 5 lesions, there were 2 cases of pleomorphic adenoma

and mucoepidermoid carcinoma each and 1 basal cell adenoma. Of the 78 cases diagnosed as neoplastic lesion on FNAC, 43 excised specimens were available for correlation which included 41 benign neoplasms and 2 malignant neoplasms. Excised specimens of all 4 cases which could not be diagnosed on FNAC and biopsy was advised.

Among 41 benign neoplasms, 35 were pleomorphic adenoma on FNAC. Of these 32 (91.4%) was confirmed by histopathology. Of the remaining 3

cases, there were epithelial-myoepithelial carcinoma, myoepithelioma and sialadenitis each.

Table 3: FNAC & HPE correlation of Non-neoplastic lesions

Type of lesion on FNAC	Number of excised specimens	Diagnosis on histopathology	Number of cases correlating/non-correlating
Inflammatory (51 cases)	3	3 sialadenitis	3 correlating
Benign cystic lesion (29 cases)	10	5 mucus retention cysts 2 pleomorphic adenoma, 2mucoepidermoid carcinoma and 1 basal cell adenoma	5 correlating 5 non-correlating

Table 4: FNAC & HPE correlation of Neoplastic benign lesions

Type of lesion on FNAC	Number of excised specimens	Diagnosis on histopathology	Number of cases correlating/non-correlating
Pleomorphic adenoma (61 cases)	35	32 pleomorphic adenoma 1 EMC 1 myoepithelioma. 1 sialadenitis	32 correlating 03 non-correlating
Monomorphic adenoma (3 cases)	2	1 pleomorphic adenoma and 1 AdCC.	01 Non-correlating 01 different histological type
Oncocytoma (2 cases)	2	Oncocytoma Acinic cell carcinoma	1 correlating 1 Non-correlating
Myoepithelioma (1 case)	1	Myoepithelioma	1 correlating
Benign cystic neoplasm (2 cases)	1	Basal cell adenoma	Non-correlating

Table 5: FNAC & HPE correlation of Neoplastic malignant lesions

Type of lesion on FNAC	Number of excised specimens	Diagnosis on histopathology	Number of cases correlating/non-correlating
Carcinoma ex pleomorphic adenoma (2 cases)	1	Pleomorphic adenoma with focal atypical areas	1 non-correlating
Acinic cell carcinoma (1 case)	1	Acinic cell carcinoma	1 correlating

Table 6: Lesion where definite diagnosis was not possible on cytology

Type of lesion on FNAC	Number of excised specimens	Diagnosis on histopathology	Number of cases correlating/non-correlating
Non-neoplastic (eosinophilic proteinaceous material with few cells of histiocytic morphology) [1 case]	1	Warthin's tumor	Nil correlation
AdCC/Pleomorphic adenoma (1 case)	1	MEC	Nil correlation
Benign salivary neoplasm (1 case)	1	AdCC	Nil correlation
Malignant neoplasm (1 case)	1	Sialadenitis	Nil correlation

The photographs of Haematoxylin & Eosin staining of biopsy specimens are shown from Figure 5 to Figure 11.

Figure 5: Pleomorphic Adenoma (Lt side: H&E, x100, Myoepithelial component and Rt side: H&E, x400, Epithelial component)

Figure 6: Oncocytoma (Lt side: H&E, x100, Cohesive aggregates of oxyphil cells and Rt side: H&E, x400, Bland nuclear morphology)

Figure 7: Carcinoma ex pleomorphic adenoma (H&E, x100, Rich yield of epithelial and myoepithelial cells exhibiting mild nuclear pleomorphism)

Figure 8: Oncocytoma (Lt side: H&E, x100, Rt side: H&E, x400; Cells exhibiting acinar configuration and eosinophilic granular cytoplasm)

Figure 9: Warthin's tumor (Lt side: H&E, x100, Dense lymphoid aggregate and Rt side: H&E, x400, Epithelial cells)

Figure 10: Adenoid Cystic Carcinoma (Different magnifications showing the cribriform arrangement (swisscheese) of tumor cells and perineural invasion.)

Figure 11: Epithelial Myoepithelial Carcinoma (H&E, x100, Lt side: Papillary configuration and Rt side: Glandular configuration)

Discussion

FNAC is a widely accepted first line investigation in the diagnosis of salivary gland lesions and this helps the clinician to determine the treatment modality. The slight female preponderance observed in the present study is concordant with results available.[6-9] Most cases were in 4th-5th decades. Parotid gland was most commonly involved.[10-13] Pleomorphic adenoma was most the most common lesion encountered followed by inflammatory lesions which correlated with other studies.[9,10,15] Chronic sialadenitis is the most common inflammatory lesion encountered which is in concordance with study by Tamwekar, et al.[16] One case of pleomorphic adenoma was erroneously diagnosed as a benign cystic lesion on FNAC which could be due to the needle missing the cellular tumorous part.[17] Two mucoepidermoid carcinoma diagnosed as benign cystic lesion on FNAC showed cyst macrophages and mucoid material. The presence of thick mucus material and low scanty yield resulted in the erroneous diagnosis.[18-20] One case of pleomorphic adenoma which turned epithelial-myoepithelial carcinoma on biopsy was due to extensive aspiration of myxoid and epithelial cells and lack of myoepithelial cells.[21] Another pleomorphic adenoma diagnosed as sialadenitis was due to aspiration of chondromyxoid fragments.[22]

Monomorphic adenoma on cytology showed epithelial cells in acinar configuration with hyaline globules and pink homogenous material. It turned out adenoid cystic carcinoma on biopsy as the hyaline globule and pink homogenous material was confused with hyalinized matrix of monomorphic adenoma.[22] Oncocytoma which was diagnosed as acinic cell carcinoma on biopsy showed cells with oxyphilic cytoplasm and bland nuclear morphology on FNAC. These features together with absence of myxoid material was the reason for false diagnosis.[22] One benign cystic neoplasm on

FNAC turned out to be basal cell adenoma due to aspiration of pleomorphic epithelial cells and cystic nature of the lesion. Carcinoma ex pleomorphic adenoma which was pleomorphic adenoma with focal atypical areas on biopsy was due to aspiration of epithelial and myoepithelial cells exhibiting nuclear pleomorphism, focal squamoid differentiation and chondromyxoid stroma.[23]

Warthins tumor in FNAC revealed granular eosinophilic proteinaceous material which masked the epithelial cells and lymphocytes, this was attributed to sampling error.[24] The case of mucoepidermoid carcinoma showed epithelial cells, myxoid stroma and stromal globules and intracytoplasmic vacuoles.

One case of benign salivary neoplasm was diagnosed as Adenoid cystic carcinoma on biopsy. FNAC yielded mildly pleomorphic ductal epithelial cells and mucoid material. Morphology of epithelial cells and lack of hyaline globules or stromal fragments led to an erroneous diagnosis.

Conclusion

The diagnostic features of most common lesions of salivary glands are well documented. The sensitivity, specificity and overall accuracy rate in the present study is 80%, 73% and 93% respectively. This correlates well with other studies documented in literature.[10,24-26] To reduce pitfalls in diagnosis multiple aspirates from different sites of the tumor and aspirating the residual swelling in cystic lesions are likely steps to be followed. Hence, FNAC is a reliable, safe and inexpensive preoperative diagnostic tool for salivary gland lesions. Thus the Milan system, MSRSGC, a recent six category grading system to classify salivary gland smears, is a much beneficial approach for cytopathologists as well as treating physicians to have a clear approach to salivary gland tumours with risk of malignancy stratification, despite having

some amount of heterogeneity and morphological overlap.

Ethical Approval: This study was approved by the Clinical Research Ethics Committee of Santiniketan Medical College, Bolpur.

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